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The Role Of Financial Benefits On Informant Syndrome: Its Impact On Insurgency

Ibrahim Yusuf Shehu; Mansur Mohammed S Kudu, Buhari Bello & Lawal Muhammad Shagari & Abdullahi Mode

**Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria
&
Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto, Nigeria**

ABSTRACT

Informant activities is as old as the banditry itself, it is a means by which unscrupulous individual act as collaborators or traders who either supply vital information to the bandits or act as agents in the disposal of stolen items, especially rustled cattle. It is a consensus that to resolve the banditry puzzle, there is the need to first unbundle the knot around roles played by informants and other collaborators. Untying the knot, however, requires more than just a passive look at the issue or blanket statements and policies on the issues. The informants and local collaborators have been the fuel keeping the banditry flame alive. While informants give information on potential victims and any impending threat, other collaborators like suppliers' daily need of the gunmen also act as informants by ensuring that their clients remain safe and prosperous, they derive enormous benefits. The paper identified that the informants are the major hindrance to a successful campaign against the bandits. They have economic gain out of the criminal conduct. Government must use both human and technology to obtain intelligence in its fight against the bandits and their collaborators. Lastly the paper recommends that they should be killed in the most humiliating circumstances to serve as deterrence to others.

Keywords; Informants, Collaborators, Bandits, Economic.

INTRODUCTION

Informants' actions are much worse than bandits' activities since they provide bandits with an unfair edge over the collective well-being of the general public. The numerous efforts by our valiant security personnel, who sacrifice their comfort, including that of their families, so that we can sleep with our two eyes close is being sabotaged by the activities of informants within our communities (Daily Trust,(2024). However there must be a concerned about the conduct of informants who assist "bandits" in their neighbourhood. The Emir of Maru in Zamfara State asserted that bandits' informants are responsible for lingering insecurity in Zamfara state. " We are appealing to government and security agencies to take serious actions in addressing informants' activities in the state" he also said " most of the informants are within our communities, and they are known by people. They move freely in communities carrying out ugly activities unchecked" lastly he called on security agencies to concentrate and deal with them decisively (Premium Times 2021). Recently the Kebbi state Executive Governor has attributed the growing security challenges in his state to the activities of informants and the inadequate presence of security personnel. He made this known during a visit to Zogirma community in Bunza Local Government Area, were recently three mobile policemen were recently killed by armed assailants (Channels television 2025). According to the governor, the attackers were not Lakurawa or known bandits, but criminals allegedly invited by informants within the community. Bandits relied heavily on informants in the past because they needed them before going for attacks. They needed to have information. Others recruited to spy on the movement of security personnel and report plans by members of the community on any action against the bandits are seen as the main stumbling blocks against any move to weed out the gunmen from the

affected areas. There are also reports of increasing role of marabouts that provide bandits with luck charms and spiritual directions. The bandits are said to be reliant on them for direction on where to attack and when. Banditry warlords define their strength by the amount of arms they possess and this makes the race for more weapons unending (channels television 2025).

Surajo Mamman, had spent years operating as a cattle rustler in villages of Safana Local Government in Katsina State, but, he said, getting a gun changed the story for him. "I bought the gun for N850,000 some six years ago. Initially, it was to take revenge over the killing of my son, which I did. Afterwards, I also joined the gang," he said, disclosing that he could not count the number of persons he killed or kidnapped using the lethal weapon. "The guns were supplied to us by Tuaregs coming from Libya using camels," Mamman said, adding that the supply strategy had since evolved away from the more tortuous method to a more free and sophisticated gun running cartel.

In villages neighbouring forests where they have camps, the bandits also get and stock shops which serve as a point of recharge for them – they stock the shops and get items they need from there. You will find out that such shops are the best in such villages, and most residents know about it. It is the same with pharmacies," he said. Speaking to Daily Trust, Na-Marai said he was wooed into banditry through enticement by bandits who patronised his handmade beddings. "They would buy and pay me much more than the price. They started telling me that I would make more money if I joined them," he said.

Governor Ahmed Aliyu of Sokoto State has directed security agencies in Sokoto State to treat anyone found to be an informant the same way they treat bandits. Governor Aliyu gave this directive during his condolence visit to communities in Wurno and Rabah Local Government Areas, recently affected by bandits' attacks. He reiterated his administration unwavering commitments to tackling banditry and urge residents of rural communities to expose anyone living above their means to the relevant authorities for proper investigation (New Telegraph 2025). He expressed dismay over the activities of some unpatriotic citizens who engage in "informant syndrome" for minimal gain. He warned such individuals and their accomplices to desist from such heinous act and seek legitimate sources of livelihood, stressing that no informant will be spared under the new strategy being adopted to curb banditry in the state. "we are determined to identify and apprehend these informants and those aiding banditry in our rural communities by all means" (New Telegraph 2025).

The Punch newspaper of 29th May (2025) reported that the Katsina State Governor, Dikko Radda, has revealed that 70 to 80 percent of the perpetrators of insecurity in the state are not in the forest but rather embedded within local communities' informants. He emphasised the critical need for decisive measures from all citizens to expose these individuals, asserting that the fight against banditry cannot succeed without addressing the threat of informants. "those in the forest are getting information from those in our communities and they are the ones who are buying drugs, fuel for the bandits to ride to perpetuate their heinous crime, providing them with medication, taking ransom sum to them in the forest. I must say if we didn't deal with these informants living amongst us, we would not succeed in this fight against insecurity. We should all be responsible in this course by exposing them" (The Punch 2025).

The Bauchi State Commissioner of police Auwal Muhammad in his interview with the Punch Newspaper said that informants are more dangerous than the baandits, kidnappers; they (informats are the one giving them (bandits) the leads. They'll call them and tell them how they will come into the community and carry out their nasty acts of criminality (The Punch 2025).

How Bandits Recruits Informants

Bandits employ many tactics in wooing and recruiting informants into their fold.

- ✓ They choose from hostages they pick in communities and release the person on the condition he will be supplying them information.
- ✓ In other instances, they would make a call and threaten a particular person and make him submit to work for them in exchange for peace.
- ✓ Because of money, some others actually reach out to the bandits to give information out of malice against someone.
- ✓ The bandits are cashing in on the endemic poverty and unemployment in rural areas to recruit young people into their fold using paltry financial incentives.

Economic Benefits of Informants

1. Some informants within the community own shops and they are in the habit of selling their products to bandits at exorbitant prices, making it difficult to obtain their cooperation in addressing the security challenges.

2. One informant in one of the communities affected by insecurity was found to be selling a bottle of Coca-Cola for N3, 000; another sold fuel for N5,000 per litre to bandits.
3. Hard drugs that are usually sold for little amounts of money at pharmacies and other related centres are sold in millions of naira by community informants to bandits.

Effects on informant to the community

- ❖ Some community members often connive with bandits to abduct helpless victims, including elderly and children, majority of which some will not come back alive.
- ❖ One informant connived with bandits to abduct his biological father, who was diabetic. When the bandits brought him to their hideout, they had already bought him diabetic tablets for his daily consumption. The sum of N30 million was paid as ransom for the man, and N8 million was given to his son for compromising and allowing his own biological father to be abducted.
- ❖ Informants are known to alert bandits whenever Nigeria Air Force jets leave the airport with the aim of bombing their hideouts. The jet fighters often fail to acquire their target and frequently have to return to base due to unsuccessful operations.
- ❖ Activities of informants and bandits have left a large number of children orphaned, many house wives widowed, many houses desolate and many innocent people dead.

CONCLUSION

We should completely disregard peace as long as informants continue to support and encourage bandits, and killers who have no idea why they would be alive. These beasts have left a large number of children orphaned, widowed, innocent people dead, and numerous houses desolate.

RECOMMENDATION

- Affected communities must come forward with sensitive information that would lead to viable solutions in addressing insecurity, and such information must be treated with utmost confidentiality.
- In these uncertain times, intelligent sharing and technological warfare are the only ways to win this fight against insurgency in the country.
- Those criminals deserved to be hanged in the most humiliating manner possible.
- Helping bandits and criminality should be dealt with in line with the law of the land.
- Sponsoring an executive bill in various state houses of assemblies to make it a serious offence for anyone to serve as an informant. Death penalty is the best punishment if found guilty.
- Imams of both Jumu'at and Daily prayer mosques to sensitise their congregations on the Islamic position regarding banditry, informant activities, and other forms of criminality.
- Provision of modern tracking technology must be employed to tap communication between known bandits and the people that supply them information.
- Religious leaders must rise up to create awareness on how to curb the issues of lack of parents taking responsibility in the upbringing of their children.

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